

Challenges Encountered by Novice Teachers Using Culturally-Responsive Strategies in a Diverse Educational Setting

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Abstract

As educational environments become increasingly diverse, the need for culturally responsive teaching has gained prominence. This case study surveys the challenges encountered by novice teachers in employing culturally responsive strategies within a diverse educational setting. Utilizing a single-case study design, the research involved in-depth interviews with novice teachers. Findings reveal that novice teachers prioritize strategies such as building rapport with students, encouraging open communication, and fostering awareness of individual strengths and differences. Despite their efforts, challenges persist, including balancing cultural responsiveness with classroom expectations, sourcing culturally relevant materials, adapting lessons to meet diverse needs, and addressing student biases and stereotypes. These challenges emphasize the necessity for continuous professional development, targeted curriculum development, and effective mentorship to support novice teachers in creating equitable and inclusive learning environments. This study underscores the pivotal role of culturally-responsive strategies in fostering inclusive and effective learning environments for novice teachers.

Keywords: culturally-responsive, diverse educational setting

Introduction

Our society is becoming increasingly diverse in terms of racial, ethnic, cultural, economic, and religious diversity. As we consider what to teach, questions arise about the curriculum and instructional methods, particularly regarding how we can employ approaches that foster critical awareness and cultural connections within the content we deliver to students (Mensah, 2021). Previous research that integrated students' cultural backgrounds and instructional methods suggested that there exists a discrepancy in culture between the school environment and students' homes. The terms "culturally appropriate" and "culturally compatible" are valuable, yet they may suggest that students' cultures should adapt to mainstream culture. Students bring a collection of values, beliefs, and "funds of knowledge" from their homes and local communities, which can either align with or deviate from the culture present in schools. These backgrounds may validate the dominant societal values in social, economic, political, and cultural realms. Therefore, alternative terms like culturally responsive teaching, culturally responsive instruction, and culturally relevant pedagogy advocate for social justice by emphasizing equality and celebrating diversity (Ebersole, et. al., 2015).

In defining culturally responsive teaching, it is important to remember that educators who employ culturally responsive teaching practices recognize and value students' cultural and linguistic assets, viewing this knowledge as valuable capital to build upon rather than a hindrance to learning. These educators utilize students' personal experiences and interests as foundational elements for instructional connections that enhance student learning and development. They employ interactive, collaborative teaching methods and strategies that support students' cultural, linguistic, and racial backgrounds, integrating these approaches with evidence-based practices (Aceves & Orosco, 2014).

While teacher educators are determined in teaching using culturally responsive methods, this approach can introduce multiple layers of complexity for them. Furthermore, developing culturally responsive practices necessitates educators to build a comprehensive knowledge base that evolves with changes in students, contexts, and subject matters. This complexity is compounded by the reality that students arrive in the classroom with diverse cultural identities. Additionally, instead of offering generic strategies for teaching diversity, teacher educators should seek productive methods to comprehend the values and traditions of families and cultures that differ from their own (Ebersole, et. al., 2015).

In the past decade, educational environments have evolved significantly over time, becoming more diverse and intricate. The rapid increase of pluralistic populations from various societies contributes to a diverse student body, posing challenges for new teachers. Lew & Nelson, (2016) have found, in their study, that teachers understood culturally responsive teaching in a simplistic way and view it as cultural celebrations that are disconnected from academic learning. Document reviews and participants' feedback revealed that they had not

been well-prepared in this salient area. Further, their findings revealed that there is a significant gap between teacher education curriculum and the real fabric of schools in the area of culturally responsive teaching, classroom management, and assessment. Some concerted measures should be planned to bridge the gap between theory and practice in those areas to assist teachers in facing such challenges confidently.

In a study about the culturally responsive curriculum of an indigenous people school in the Philippines, Mercado (2020) emphasized the aspiration of indigenous and/or marginalized communities for an education that acknowledges their context, respects their identities, and upholds the significance of their traditional knowledge, skills, and cultural heritage. He also concluded that in implementing a culturally responsive curriculum in the classroom, teachers anchor the content and competencies on the ancestral domain and cultural practices of the students but the teachers' understanding of cultural practices is limited to superficial knowledge. Moreover, Paculaba & Mangila (2020) claimed that when striving to intrinsically motivate a diverse group of students, educators need to consider not only the classroom and school culture but also external factors that affect students. To effectively address personal challenges, curriculum and instruction must be culturally relevant, responsive, appropriate, and sensitive to the learner.

Culturally responsive pedagogy is essential in education, honoring diverse backgrounds to foster inclusive learning environments. Acknowledging students' backgrounds enhances academic achievement and engagement, while fostering positive relationships promotes a sense of belonging and well-being. Tailoring instruction to meet diverse needs improves outcomes. Promoting critical consciousness empowers students to challenge stereotypes and confront social injustices. Continuous professional development and support are crucial for successful implementation of these strategies. Addressing these areas enables educational institutions to establish equitable and inclusive environments. However, further research is necessary to explore effective strategies for acknowledging cultural backgrounds, examine the impact of inclusive communities, investigate approaches for diverse learning needs, and evaluate outcomes related to promoting critical consciousness (Caingcoy, 2023).

Despite various accounts detailing the challenges met by teachers in teaching and the benefits of their strategies and methods, there remains a gap in the specific culturally-responsive strategies used by novice teachers and their effectiveness in a diverse educational setting. This study aims to address this gap by identifying specific challenges encountered by novice teachers in using culturally-responsive strategies in a diverse educational setting, what strategies were used, how these strategies were implemented, and why these strategies were chosen.

Research Questions

In the light of exploring specific challenges met by novice teachers in the use of culturally responsive strategies in a diverse educational setting, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What are specific culturally-responsive strategies employed by novice teachers in a diverse educational setting, such as the classroom?
2. How are these culturally-responsive strategies implemented in a diverse educational setting, such as the classroom?
3. Why were these culturally-responsive strategies preferred by novice teachers?
4. What are the specific challenges met by novice teachers in the use of culturally-responsive strategies in a diverse educational setting?

Literature Review

Teachers demonstrate awareness of cultural diversity in their classrooms and exhibit positive attitudes towards it. This is evident when they express concerns and raise issues related to their students, and when they proactively engage in reading and researching to better understand their students' cultural backgrounds (Idrus & Sohid, 2023). Compelling research highlights the benefits of culturally responsive teaching. In a culturally responsive classroom, the diverse identities and experiences of learners are acknowledged, respected, and utilized to connect with challenging new learning opportunities. This personalized approach to instruction benefits all students. However, culturally responsive teaching raises the question as to which students do not have access to this type of culturally relevant instruction (Muñiz, 2019).

Educators need to consider how students' diverse backgrounds impact their learning and adopt teaching methods that accommodate this increasing diversity in race, culture, language, and prior knowledge (Kieran & Anderson, 2018). Varner & Seriki (2011) presented a multifaceted and complex call to teachers to reflexively and critically analyze how personal narratives reflect identity and privilege. A thorough examination of our own narratives, especially in how they highlight overrepresented identity aspects, offers a way to address how teachers' pedagogical beliefs and practices are influenced. Similarly, there are significant and beneficial implications when educators comprehend identity, particularly in the context of teacher narrative and identity development.

Creating a classroom environment that supports all learners, regardless of their backgrounds, is crucial for their future success as professionals. Therefore, it is essential for faculty to design courses with the needs of all students in consideration (Woodley, et. al., 2017). Little is known about the culturally responsive teaching knowledge and practices of most teachers who teach students of color, LGBTQ students, religious minority

students, and international students. Knowledge gaps encompass several aspects: the awareness and consideration of issues related to students' cultural backgrounds among teachers, their adoption and valuation of culturally responsive practices, their perceived strengths and areas for improvement in these practices, and potential variations in cultural responsiveness across different education sectors and levels of instruction (Heitner & Jennings, 2016). To be culturally responsive, teachers must possess the capacity to empathize with all individuals who are different and vulnerable to marginalization, and they must implement strategies to address inequities faced by students in their schools. A culturally responsive teacher not only demonstrates distributed and instructional leadership but also ensures that every student's voice is heard. They integrate the cultural values and norms of a diverse student body and support teachers' pedagogical practices in response to the needs of students from various backgrounds (Brown, et. al., 2022). In the Philippine contexts, handling students who come from different places is different from facilitating learning in regular schools. One obvious challenge can be rooted in the presence of multiculturalism where teachers have to adjust the curriculum in order to partially if not totally cater all the learners (Dizon & Nanquil, 2024). Teachers' educational practices highlight flexibility and sensitivity to culturally diverse students' differences, diversity, and learning experiences. Despite some notable challenges in employing instruction, teachers have become resilient to provide students with meaningful experiences in teaching the lesson's contents (Protacio, 2022).

Culturally responsive teaching emphasizes leveraging cultural knowledge, past experiences, reference frameworks, and performance styles to enhance the effectiveness of learning experiences for ethnically diverse learners. Elements such as cultural diversity awareness, ethnic and cultural curriculum, learning communities, culturally sensitive communication, and inclusive instructional practices all contribute to providing equitable access to education for students from diverse backgrounds. These practices create a welcoming learning environment where students feel safe to express themselves authentically and believe that their contributions and perspectives are valued and respected (Cheng et. al., 2021). In the same manner, the growing diversity in Philippine schools presents both opportunities and challenges. Diverse classrooms and schools allow for the education of students from various cultures and provide opportunities for learning cooperative and productive coexistence. Teachers must acquire the knowledge and skills needed to leverage the benefits of diversity while effectively managing its challenges (Tipan, et.al., 2020).

Cultural diversity not only creates divides among people but also serves as a means to unite them, fostering mutual understanding through diverse perspectives and optimistic worldviews. (Inocian, et. al., 2020). In today's globalized world, educational institutions are becoming increasingly diverse, mirroring the multicultural makeup of society. This diversity brings both challenges and opportunities for school leaders as they manage the complexities of leadership in culturally varied environments. Therefore, there is an increasing imperative to investigate cross-cultural leadership dynamics within educational settings to better meet the diverse needs of student populations (Uy, et. al., 2024).

Research Method

Research Design

To explore the culturally responsive strategies employed by teachers in a diverse educational setting, this study used a single-case study design. This design was chosen by the researchers since the study focused on an issue or concern of a single group within a bounded system, in this case, the teachers.

Informants of the Study

The participants of this study were three (3) novice faculty members teaching in a university. The researchers aim to highlight that being in a university brings about culturally diverse students, thus, a diverse educational setting. The participants were chosen based on their length of service in teaching: less than one year.

Data Collection Instrument

In this study, the researchers conducted one-on-one interviews with the participants using a semi-structured questionnaire to identify the culturally responsive strategies they employ in the classroom, how these strategies are implemented, why these strategies were preferred, and the challenges they encountered in the use of these strategies in a culturally-diverse setting.

Data Analysis

The Thematic Analysis (TA) was utilized as the method for data analysis. As Braun and Clarke (2006) describe, TA is a method for systematically identifying, organizing, and offering insight into patterns of meaning (themes) across a data set. By focusing on meaning across the data set, TA allows researchers to see and make sense of collective or shared meanings and experiences. This approach is particularly well-suited for examining the qualitatively rich data obtained through one-on-one interviews with faculty members. This enabled researchers to systematically identify, analyze, and report patterns or themes related to the challenges met by novice teachers in the use of culturally responsive strategies in a diverse educational setting. By coding and organizing the data into key themes, thematic analysis facilitated a comprehensive understanding of the strategies employed by teachers, their implementation methods, the reasons behind their preferences, and the challenges they've

met.

Findings and Discussion

This presents the results and discussion of the study, which aimed to determine the challenges encountered by novice teachers in the use of culturally-responsive strategies in a diverse educational setting. The data collected were collected through an interview with three (3) novice teachers, and the data are presented in tabular format, followed by analysis and interpretation.

Table 1. Culturally-Responsive Strategies Employed by Novice Teachers

Themes	Responses
<p><i>Theme 1:</i></p> <p>Building rapport/ connection with students</p>	<p>"I see a lot of barriers that exist within the four walls of the classroom. I see to it that I establish a respectable and honest relationship between me and my students, even at the start of the class or semester."</p> <p>"My students are varied. They are really different, in terms of how they deal with the tasks given to them or to their classmates. As a teacher, I always maintain a good relationship with them, so that there is a mutual understanding between everybody inside the classroom. That despite the differences, they will still understand each other."</p> <p>"...building rapport with my students is one of my priorities in class..."</p> <p>"Students have a need to connect with their peers and also their teachers. I will make sure to do that."</p>
<p><i>Theme 2:</i></p> <p>Encouraging open communication</p>	<p>"...even during recitation, I encourage them to share their ideas and thoughts, through any language they are comfortable with."</p> <p>"I am open to anything they want to share with the class. I do not interrupt them even if what they are saying is technically wrong. As long as they have ideas, I accept them."</p> <p>"My classroom is an open classroom. We accept each other's ideas, anything that they want to share to the class. I learn through their sharings also."</p> <p>"I make sure to maintain open communication in the classroom. I don't interrupt them whenever they want to share something. I want them to feel free to share their ideas. Or if there is something they don't like about how I manage the class, or the class rules, I solicit their opinion also."</p> <p>"I have students who aren't allowed to wear pants because of religious reasons. So when they came to me to raise their concern, I just allowed them to wear skirt even during P.E. classes."</p>
<p><i>Theme 3:</i></p> <p>Fostering awareness of students' strengths and weaknesses</p>	<p>"I am an advocate of multiple intelligences. I always make it a point to consider what my students can and can't do. In a diverse classroom, I think it's always important to hone your students' strengths and improve on their weaknesses."</p> <p>"If there is a task that they're good at, I encourage them to work on that particular area so that they'll get better at it."</p> <p>I am aware that my students came from different families, thus, they have different culture. They have different talents and abilities, depending on how they were raised by their parents. I always check what they're good at and what areas need improvement."</p>
<p><i>Theme 4:</i></p> <p>Promoting respect and awareness of individual differences</p>	<p>"...I always encourage them to be more open to each other's differences..."</p> <p>"...even during prayer, before and after the class, I always make it a point to do an interfaith prayer, so that the students will know that there is not just one religion. We have different beliefs and we should respect that."</p> <p>"I always remind them to be more tolerant of other people's practices, however different they are from our own."</p> <p>"...if we can just try to understand that we have diverse learners inside the classroom, as teachers, we will be more responsive to their needs."</p>

The responses of the participants regarding the culturally-responsive strategies they employ in the classroom resulted in four (4) themes: building rapport/ connection with students, encouraging open communication, fostering awareness of students' strengths and weaknesses, and promoting respect and awareness of individual

differences. This study aimed to determine the challenges encountered by novice teachers in the use of culturally-responsive strategies in a diverse educational setting. Data revealed that novice teachers use culturally-responsive strategies that cultivate empathetic and inclusive student relationships. This shows that culturally-responsive teaching and cultivating empathetic and inclusive relationships are interconnected concepts that are vital in a diverse classroom.

Table 2. Novice Teachers' Implementation of Culturally Responsive Strategies in a Diverse Educational Setting

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Responses</i>
Theme 1: Student involvement in the creation of classroom rules	"On the very first day of class, I set the rules first. I also ask them if they are okay with the rules that I've set, or if they have suggestions." "...I really want that there is open communication in the classroom. So I always ask my students if they are okay with that. With sharing...sharing. Like that." "Since my students are diverse, I really want them to voice out about what they want to happen inside the classroom. If they are okay with this and that. So that I can cater their diverse needs."
Theme 2: Differentiated instruction	"...activities must be varied..." "Students have different abilities, so if possible, give varied activities." "I always make it a point to provide varied activities to my students to cater to the diverse needs of each learner." "...regarding my teaching methods, I make sure to adapt them to the needs of my students..."
Theme 3: Multiple perspectives and cultural viewpoints	"As a teacher, I always make sure to update my knowledge about cultural differences and trends. As I do this, I also share it with my students." "My students are already mature individuals, so I'm sure they already understand about cultural differences in the classroom, and other differences for that matter. I just make sure to update their knowledge and encourage them to be more open with these kinds of things." "I think respect is just a matter of understanding and acceptance. If my students understand and accept each other's differences and encourage others to do the same, everyone's perspectives about cultural diversity will be the same, and somehow, we will meet somewhere in the middle. This is what I always encourage my students to do." "...I always encourage them open-minded individuals and always bear in mind each person is different from the other..." "Whenever I can, I let them explore topics of interest regarding cultural differences and integrate them into the lesson."

The responses of the participants regarding how they implement culturally-responsive strategies in a diverse educational setting resulted in three (3) themes: student involvement in the creation of classroom rules, differentiated instruction, and multiple perspectives and cultural viewpoints. The study also revealed that in terms of implementing these culturally-responsive strategies in the classroom, novice teachers promote a student-centered, inclusive, and differentiated learning environment. These elements, combined, create a dynamic and supportive learning environment where all students feel valued.

Table 3. Reasons for the Preferences of Novice Teachers in Choosing Culturally-Responsive Strategies in the Classroom

Themes	Responses
Theme 1: Developing a Deeper Understanding of Students	<p>"...if I know them better, I can understand them better. So, our relationship is lighter and better both inside and outside the classroom."</p> <p>"There is a connection between me and my students, so it's easier to understand and respect each other, or one another."</p> <p>"I want my students to see me not just as a teacher, but also someone who they can share with."</p> <p>"I want to be open to them, and them to be open to me. I don't want to be a terror teacher. But of course, there are still certain boundaries as teacher and students."</p> <p>"I think they learn better if there is open communication in class. They are more relaxed, and can understand the lessons better. They are more willing to share. So I also learn better about them."</p>
Theme 2: Increasing Motivation to Learn	<p>"...they are more excited in class, more eager..."</p> <p>"They are more comfortable in the classroom and the learning process gets easier."</p> <p>"...they're motivated to learn, especially if the activities I give are varied. They're more motivated to explore..."</p> <p>"I notice that students are more motivated to learn if there is a welcoming classroom environment. So, I see to it that I maintain open communication with my students, no matter how diverse they are."</p>
Theme 3: Maintaining a Positive Classroom Climate	<p>"As a student, I learn better if there is a positive vibe in the classroom. I want my students to feel the same."</p> <p>"...they feel welcomed...and seen..."</p> <p>"Despite their differences and diversity, I want them to feel welcomed in the class."</p> <p>"I want my classroom to be a place of open communication, of sharing ideas and thoughts. I want my students to have fun while learning."</p>

The responses of the participants regarding the reasons for their preferences in choosing culturally-responsive strategies in the classroom resulted in three (3) themes: developing a deeper understanding of students, increasing motivation to learn, and maintaining a positive classroom climate. Data revealed that the participants have chosen their preferred culturally-responsive strategies with the goal of building a supportive and motivating learning community.

Table 4. Challenges Met by Novice Teachers in the Use of Culturally-Responsive Strategies in a Diverse Educational Setting

Themes	Responses
<p>Theme 1:</p> <p>Maintaining a balance between cultural responsiveness and classroom expectations</p>	<p>"Implementing culturally-responsive strategies inside the classroom, sometimes it's easier said than done. As a teacher you wish to be culturally-responsive, but at the same time, you also want to enforce rules that might otherwise deviate from being culturally-responsive. But rules are rules, right? Without them, the classroom would be a mess. So, sometimes, it's really difficult to strike a balance."</p> <p>"...sometimes torn between living up to what an ideal classroom should be versus what is expected of me as a teacher..."</p> <p>"...to what extent are we supposed to be culturally-responsive, that line is not clear sometimes..."</p>
<p>Theme 2:</p> <p>Finding culturally-relevant materials</p>	<p>"...even in photos, being culturally-responsive is not always evident..."</p> <p>"As Filipinos, sometimes, we are more prone to side towards our own biases, like white-skinned people, something like that. And these things are evident in the materials that are available for use. Good thing that we have the internet nowadays, it's easier to find other materials."</p> <p>"...sometimes it's difficult to judge whether the material I'm presenting is considered to be culturally-responsive or not..."</p> <p>"Given the materials that are available, books, for example, there are instances that only white skinned people are presented as examples, only Catholic religion is mentioned. So sometimes, I just tweak it a little bit. Or I create my own examples, like pictures from the internet."</p>
<p>Theme 3:</p> <p>Adapting the lessons to meet diverse needs</p>	<p>"...it's really a challenge because there are a lot of things to consider, like how do I make the lesson culturally-responsive?"</p> <p>"It's easier said than done. My major challenge is how do I pattern my lessons to the diverse needs of my students. Even if I do differentiated instruction, like I provide varied activities, there is still the question if the lesson or the content itself is in line with what I am trying to do, to be culturally-responsive."</p> <p>"I always need to consider and think about if my lessons are culturally-responsive. Like how I integrate this concept to my lessons."</p> <p>"My students are diverse, I am aware of that. And they have diverse needs. I always see to it that I provide different activities. But I also want to integrate being culturally-responsive in the lesson itself. And sometimes, I find that difficult."</p>
<p>Theme 4:</p> <p>Addressing stereotypes and biases</p>	<p>"College students are quite exposed to a lot of things already, especially now, with the influence of social media. Sometimes, they have certain judgements and opinions about certain things that are difficult to address because that's what's already imprinted in their minds."</p> <p>"...students have biases that are difficult to change..."</p> <p>"As a teacher, my intentions are good, because I want to raise awareness among my students about cultural responsiveness. But sometimes, I'm misunderstood by my students because they already have these certain biases about things they believe in."</p> <p>"One of the challenges that I often encounter is how to manage or address the biases of my students. Especially in the case of my students who are members of the LGBTQIA community. Of course, they have beliefs that they should be given freedom to wear whatever they want, or say whatever they want. Sometimes it's difficult to let them understand about certain limitations that exist in the classroom, because as students, they still have to adhere to the rules, like wearing the prescribed uniform. But I try my best to make them understand, it's just quite a challenge to do it."</p>

The responses of the participants regarding the challenges they've encountered in the use of culturally-responsive strategies in a diverse educational setting resulted in four (4) themes: maintaining a balance between cultural responsiveness and classroom expectations, finding culturally-relevant materials, adapting the lessons to meet diverse needs, and addressing stereotypes and biases. The study revealed that in terms of using culturally-responsive strategies in a diverse educational setting such as the classroom, novice teachers find difficulty in navigating cultural complexities in instruction. Most of the challenges found were in maintaining a balance between cultural responsiveness and classroom expectations, finding culturally-relevant materials, adapting the lessons to meet diverse needs, and addressing stereotypes and biases. This encompasses a delicate interplay between cultural responsiveness, curriculum adaptation, and addressing biases.

The researchers identified recurring patterns and themes in the participants' responses using Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase approach: familiarization, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and interpreting the produced results. This involved a process of comprehensive understanding, coding, and categorizing information into meaningful bits. Braun and Clarke (2006) emphasize that thematic analysis is a flexible method adaptable to various research contexts for exploring complex phenomena and understanding participants' perspectives in depth.

Conclusion

This study underscores the pivotal role of culturally-responsive strategies in fostering inclusive and effective learning environments for novice teachers. There shows a strong relationship between culturally-responsive teaching and cultivating empathetic and inclusive student relationships, underscoring their interconnectedness in creating a supportive classroom climate. Novice teachers demonstrated a commitment to student-centered, inclusive, and differentiated practices, aiming to build a motivating learning community. However, navigating cultural complexities, including maintaining balance between cultural responsiveness and classroom expectations, locating culturally relevant materials, adapting instruction, and addressing biases, emerged as significant challenges. These findings highlight the need for ongoing professional development and support for novice teachers to effectively implement culturally responsive strategies and create equitable learning experiences for all students.

Further Research

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are suggested:

Curriculum development. Investigate the development of culturally-relevant and responsive curricula that effectively address the diverse needs of students.

Teacher education: Examine how teacher preparation programs can better equip novice teachers with the knowledge and skills to navigate cultural complexities.

In-depth case studies: Conduct detailed case studies of novice teachers to explore the specific challenges they face in navigating cultural complexities in diverse classrooms.

Mentorship programs: Develop effective mentorship programs to support novice teachers in implementing culturally-responsive practices.

Collaborative research: Partner with schools and districts to implement and evaluate large-scale culturally-responsive initiatives.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A *Interview Questionnaire*

Teacher's Demographic Profile

Name (*Optional*): _____

Age: _____ Sex: _____

Months of Teaching Experience: _____

Length of Service in the Current Workplace: _____

Part 1. Participant Background

Please describe your teaching background, including your education, years of experience, and current teaching role.

- What subjects or year levels do you teach?
- Have you had any formal training in culturally-responsive teaching?
- How would you describe the diversity of your current classroom?
- What kinds of diversity (e.g., cultural, linguistic, socio-economic) are present in your classroom?

Part 2: Identification of Culturally Responsive Strategies

- What culturally-responsive strategies do you use in your classroom? Please provide examples of these strategies.
- What influenced your preference of these strategies over others?
- Were there any particular challenges or successes that guided your choice?

Part 3: Implementation of Strategies

- How do you implement these culturally-responsive strategies in your daily teaching?
- How do you consider students' cultural backgrounds into your teaching and teaching activities?
- What are specific practices you use to acknowledge and value students' cultural differences?
- How does a typical lesson involving these strategies look like?
- How do you prepare and plan for implementing these strategies?

What resources or supports do you use when implementing these strategies?

- Do you rely on any specific materials, tools, or professional development resources?
- How do you adapt or modify these resources (if there are any) to fit your classroom needs?

Part 4. Challenges in the Implementation of Strategies

- What challenges have you encountered in the implementation of these strategies?
- Are there any barriers to implementing these strategies effectively?
- Can you describe the primary challenges you've encountered while implementing culturally-responsive strategies in your classroom?
- How do you define cultural responsiveness, and how does this definition influence your teaching practices and your ability to tackle challenges?
- How have you adapted your approach in response to these challenges?